

Report D3.5

“Report on domains ontology requirements and specifications”

Grant Agreement: 958371

OntoCommons - Ontology-driven data documentation for Industry Commons, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 958371.

Project Title	Ontology-driven data documentation for Industry Commons
Project Acronym	OntoCommons
Project Number	958371
Type of project	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topics	DT-NMBP-39-2020 - Towards Standardised Documentation of Data through taxonomies and ontologies (CSA)
Starting date of Project	01 November 2020
Duration of the project	36 months
Website	www.ontocommons.eu

Report D3.5

“Report on domains ontology requirements and specifications”

Work Package	WP3 Industrial Domain Ontologies
Task	T3.3 Formalising domain-specific requirements
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Version	Final
Date	27/09/2023

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	02/03/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Creation of Deliverable Template
0.2	04/04/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Required sections created
0.3	05/04/2023	Lan Yang	UC19 requirements updated
0.4	22/04/2023	Hedi Karray	Reviewed requirements
0.5	10/05/ 2023	Lan Yang	UC19 functional requirements updated
0.6	29/06/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Created section for requirement guideline
0.7	15/07/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Updated section for requirement guideline
0.8	30/07/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Created section for FAIRness of requirements
0.9	15/08/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Data for UC9 updated
1.0	30/08/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Data for UC2 updated
1.1	15/09/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Version 0.1 completed
1.2	17/09/2023	Hedi Karray	Reviewed and commented
1.3	25/09/2023	Arkopaul Sarkar	Version 0.2 completed
1.4	25/09/2023	Hedi Karray	Review completed
1.5	27/09/2023	Nadja Adamovic	Approval and submission

Keywords

Ontology; Domain-level ontology; Requirement; Competency question; Material; Manufacturing; Maintenance; Systems; Products; Services; Enterprise

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

OntoCommons aims at working towards interoperability by means of harmonization with respect to upper-level ontologies and facilitating agreement in domain ontology development. As part of the effort of work package 3, an objective of OntoCommons is to collect and formalize requirements from the stakeholders' community by domain in terms of ontology development and exploitation. This report presents a set of functional and non-functional requirements based on the needs of demonstrators but also from stakeholders' (including domain experts') inputs - from inside and outside the project - collected through a set of expert group meetings and workshops. This deliverable (D3.5) is an extension of the 3.4 deliverable on the collection of such requirements driven by the data provided by the demonstrators. This deliverable will serve as input for the investigation of intra- and cross-domain interoperability in Task 3.4, as well as for the ontology knowledge graph validation in Task 4.6.

The primary challenge for preparing this deliverable arose from the long interactions and negotiations with the demonstrators' organisations regarding the collection of data. Although the members of T3.3 envisioned collecting significant amount of data from the use cases, it faced hurdles in overcoming the security and privacy concerns of the companies regarding sharing their proprietary data. The members were obligated to change their strategy repeatedly to achieve the goal to some extent, delaying the completion of the report. This report contains at least some data sets acquired from few demonstrators to that end.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	8
1.1 Summary of first report on domain ontology requirements and specifications.....	8
1.2 Purpose of deliverable.....	9
1.3 Scope of deliverable.....	9
2. LOT4OCES ontology requirement specification guide.....	9
2.1 Gaps of LOT in Ontology requirement specification steps.	10
2.1.1 Use Case Specification.....	10
2.1.2 Data Exchange Identification	10
2.1.3 Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSB)	11
2.1.4 Functional Ontology requirements Formalisation	12
2.2 Ontology Requirement Specification Guide	13
3. Use Case Specification - <identifier/name>	16
4. Analysis of requirement for new use case.....	28
5. Data Collection from Use Case	30
5.1 UC9: Ontology-based Maintenance.....	30
5.2 UC2: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing.....	35
6. Persistence of Requirement Data	37
6.1 Annotation of requirement data.....	37
6.1 FAIRness of requirement data	39
7. Conclusions	43

List of Figures

Figure 1: BPMN diagram for ontology requirement specification phase.....	15
Figure 2: Overview of UC19.....	28
Figure 3: Ontology model for representing ORSD.....	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Roles of team members engaged in ontology requirement specification.....	13
Table 2: Use case specification template	16
Table 3: Data set/Data exchange specification template.....	19
Table 4: Functional requirement specification template.....	24
Table 5: Glossary template	26
Table 6: Ontology requirement specification template.....	27
Table 7: ORSD document for UC19.....	28
Table 8: Competency questions for UC19	29
Table 9: Description of data set 1 for UC9	30
Table 10: Description of data set 2 for UC9	32
Table 11: Description of data set 1 for UC2	35
Table 12: metadata for the FDP	40
Table 13: Metadata for catalogues containing ORSD for use cases.....	41
Table 14: Metadata for catalogues containing ORSD for domain requirements	41
Table 15: Example metadata of ORSD resource for UC11 Siemens.....	42

1.Introduction

The work package 3 (WP3) of the OntoCommons project aims at intra- and cross-domain interoperability by harmonizing domain ontologies. The Task 3.3 of the WP3 specifically focuses on reviewing and formalizing common requirements for a standardized suite of domain ontologies, the latter including both newly developed and existing ontologies in domains such as materials modelling and manufacturing. As suggested by the project charter, the requirements will be formed not only based on the needs of demonstrators but also from stakeholders' (domain experts') inputs - from inside and outside the project - collected through a set of expert group meetings and workshops.

In this deliverable, we present a detailed amendment to the ontology requirement specification phase of LOT methodology to mitigate various challenges faced while applying the methodology stemming from lack of detailed guidance and lack of coordination among the steps. At the same time, this report analysed some of the new use cases collected from the demonstrators who joined the project after the first report (D3.4) was completed. Lastly, we made effort in making the results of T3.3 persistent by storing the requirements in a knowledge graph with SPARQL end points for easy management of the records and to make the data FAIR.

1.1 Summary of first report on domain ontology requirements and specifications

This first report on ontology requirement specification (D3.4) presented the domain level requirements as specifications for the ontology exploitation and harmonization under OntoCommons ecosystem. The requirements were collected closely following a standardized ontology engineering methodology (LOT) with some adjustments to fit the purpose of covering a wide range of domains. The methodology is detailed in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** of D3.4. The requirements were collected through several workshops and meetings, totalling 17, with participation from use case owners, partners, project members and domain experts, including from outside the projects. Besides, the task members met bi-weekly for the past three months to analyse, plan, and organize the requirements. After formal and informal interviews with WP5 partners, we collected (in January 2022) in total 341 competency questions with "accepted status" from the use case partners; among them, we observed that 20% (70 CQs) are related to Tekniker use case; 11% (40 CQs) are related to Siemens and same for Bosch. The use case Adige SpA provides 9% (34 CQs), Airbus defines 9% (32 CQs), and ElvalHalcor S.A. specifies 8% (30 CQs) and; the other use cases (UKRISTFC and GCL, OAS, and Fraunhofer, and IRES) specifies between 21 to 11 use CQs. Figure 5 details the number of the collected CQs over the 11 use cases.

Because the use cases do not directly correspond to the domain as requirements related to a particular domain can be found in multiple use cases, the report D3.4 also aimed to collate the use case requirements for a specific domain area and expand them to increase coverage of that domain. The list of domain areas were derived in the overall scope of the OntoCommons project, namely, material science and manufacturing (NMBP domains) and the landscape analysis conducted under T3.2 (Le Franc et al., 2022). The competency questions from use cases are classified and then more competency questions are added to increase the coverage of each domain, totalling 406 competency questions (144 for manufacturing, 81 for materials science, 23 for products and services, 71 for systems engineering, 53 for maintenance, and 34 for Enterprise.

D3.4 presents the non-functional and functional requirements respectively for both use cases and domain areas. The report also includes a list of technical requirements that needed to be decided before the ontology harmonization and development. A glossary of terms extracted from the competency questions is included in Appendix of the report.

1.2 Purpose of deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to amend the list of requirements presented in the first version with newly analysed requirements from the new batch of demonstrators use cases acquired after the publication of the first report, to provide sample data associated with the use case requirements, present a strategy to publish the requirements in a publicly accessible repository with proper FAIR metadata, and most importantly present a ontology requirement specification guide based on the observations and experience garnered through the work in T3.3.

1.3 Scope of deliverable

The deliverable captures ontology requirements in domains such as materials and manufacturing as needed by the demonstrators and agreed upon by the wider community of stakeholders.

2.LOT4OCES ontology requirement specification guide

OntoCommons requirement analysis was conducted using LOT methodology. During the work, we observed some shortcomings of LOT methodology and needed to adjust it or devise more details for performing the steps. The observations were included in the recommended guide presented in Section 2.2 as part of LOT4OCES. Although LOT4OCES covers the entire ontology engineering methodology, we only focus on the requirement specification phase in this report. Before presenting the guide, various observations and recommendations collected through the

experience of implementing LOT as well as surveys conducted as part of D4.7 to collect feedbacks from demonstrators who use LOT in their ontology development process.

2.1 Gaps of LOT in Ontology requirement specification steps.

2.1.1 *Use Case Specification*

The LOT methodology provides some examples of use cases consisting of information such as textual description, actor, and flow. However, the methodology does not provide a specific template on required information to be collected as part of use case specification. Most of the use cases provide a high level mission and vision of their project which focus on the application or use of the data. It is very important for the domain expert and ontology engineers to interview users to extract more information on the data related activities. A list of standard questionnaire will be helpful for domain experts and ontology engineers to curate necessary information as part of use case specification. In OntoCommons, demonstrators were surveyed with a form asking questions on not only the description, actors, and flow, but also pre-condition and post-condition of their scenario, data sources, relevant vocabulary, technology readiness level, and KPIs. Descriptions of use cases could be found in D5.2. It is observed that user representative may not always be aware of the data specification practical scenario. Domain experts should make effort in interpreting the data requirements from use case descriptions. For this purpose, flow charts, system diagram, and ER diagram supplied by users may be helpful. Moreover, the use case may require other developments in the systems and software apart from the ontology. It is a responsibility of domain expert and ontology engineers to delineate the ontology development through a two-way dialogue with the users to correctly identify the scope of the work regarding ontology development and document the same in the use case specification.

As observed in our survey, for the continuation of earlier projects on Ontology development in the same organisation, users may want to reuse parts of those developments. Such information regarding existing ontology related to the use case, technological infrastructure, software, and various other learnings and pitfalls also need to be included in the use case specification. In the end, the use case specification should include the improvements or achievements expected by in terms of quantifiable measures, e.g., KPIs and TRLs.

2.1.2 *Data Exchange Identification*

In this phase the documentation is collected on: datasets, regulations, standards, data formats, APIs specifications, database schemas, etc. Although LOT workflow mentions this step as a complimentary step, in our past experiences and the survey of other projects, the difficulties in

acquiring these information are observed. Companies are not always ready to share confidential data or API specifications. The users also may not be aware of the database schema deep inside the back end infrastructure or because of the obscurity imposed by the systems customer is using. Additionally, a description of various data models and API specification need to be understood unambiguously as the former are often data centric and the latter is more application centric. Many of these problems may be mitigated by adopting a FAIR data principles to describe the data as FAIR metadata no only describe the data but also provide some level of assurance to the customers on the privacy and security of their data.

2.1.3 *Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD)*

Once the ontology development team has all the information about the requirements, obtained from the “purpose and scope identification”, “ontological requirements proposal” and “ontological requirements completion” activities, the Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) is created. This specification document stores all the functional and non-functional requirements identified and the information associated to them. In our past experiences and the survey conducted on LOT adopters, ORSD is a proven way to document ontology requirements.

The purpose and scope fields need to clearly delineate the work to be carried out in the ontology front. Therefore these two statements are required to be extracted from the broad use case specification as mentioned in Sec. 5.4.1. Users may need to be involved in this phase providing review and final approval as an agreement on the intended coverage of the work.

Another important section that is often overlooked is the “intended use”. This section may be adopted for describing the use case, the systems and their components (including associated diagrams and charts), data flows, and user and system interactions which are to be impacted by the ontology development. As there is no specific section to provide the user story, this section may also be adopted for providing one, if available.

The non-functional requirement section is generally use to capture information on existing ontology or standards to be reused, instruction on metadata and multi-lingual support. Several other concerns regarding ontology development may also be mentioned if given by the customers. These include IRI structure, encoding formats, expressivity of the language and recommended reasoners to be used, various evaluation criteria, documentation and publication strategies as well and code development infrastructure, e.g., code repository, issue and bug management tool, integration and deployment tool etc. If these information are not available from the client then they need to be decided during implementation phase by the ontology engineers by understanding the client’s situation through discussions and negotiations.

Although pre-glossary terms are mentioned as optional by LOT, especially in case of functional requirements captured in concept table, we found its importance in most of the projects. Coming up a glossary from CQs and answers is particularly important in large projects for prioritising the work based on importance derived from the frequency of the terms. However, ORSD does not specifically mention a format for creating such glossary. A standardised template for this purpose is necessary.

2.1.4 *Functional Ontology requirements Formalisation*

Although LOT mentions three alternative methods to write functional requirements for the ontology, competency questions are most popular method. This is evident from the work of OntoCommons demonstrators surveyed. However, CQs are often written in a way that is easier to be converted to SPARQL, making them only looking for explicitly asserted information from the knowledge base. This is often a weak use of CQs. For more effective use of CQ in the evaluation, it is important to form CQs in a way that requires implicit information that to be inferred by the axioms or rules in the ontology. It is also needs to be remembered that many other forms of query and validation tools except SPARQL, e.g, SQWRL, SHACL, and DL Query may be used evaluating the CQs in the testing phase. This makes writing CQs the most crucial as well as difficult part of the ontology requirement specification.

Coming up with quality CQs requires concerted effort from ontology engineers, users and domain experts. It is also a responsibility of the ontology engineers to educate the users to read and interpret CQs to ensure their involvement and help them to review CQs according to completion criteria. Another way to mitigate the challenge is to write the CQs in two phases: 1) informal CQs to be written by users with the help of ontology engineers and domain experts and 2) formal CQs to be developed by ontology engineers by rewriting the informal CQs with formal terminologies.

The template for writing CQs from Vlcinity project, available as part of LOT resources is an useful template to be used, however we found different projects using their own template or writing them directly in the Functional Requirement section of ORSD template.

The CQs need to be evaluated for completion by applying a list of criteria e.g., completeness, correctness, consistency, verifiability, comprehensibility, unambiguity, conciseness. Some of these criteria may be difficult to assess as per our experience from last projects, and requirement engineering for OntoCommons demonstrators. Some of these difficulties are mentioned in Section 5 of D3.3. In summary, the criteria are difficult to apply for domain ontology reference or upper level ontology development. If the scope of the work is not defined, some of the criteria will be difficult to apply. The judgement is often subjective therefore it requires to involve multiple sources to truth, engaging multiple representatives from both users and ontology engineers.

2.2 Ontology Requirement Specification Guide

R1: Whether the purpose is the development of domain or application-level ontology or data modelling using existing or developed ontology, the ontology development team **SHOULD** undertake activities under the Ontology requirements specification at the beginning of the ontology development project as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

R1.1: The ontology development team **SHOULD** include members with roles of Product owners, Domain experts, and Ontology analysts for performing activities under Ontology requirements specification.

Table 1: Roles of team members engaged in ontology requirement specification

Role	Responsibility	Required skill
Product owner	To provide a clear vision of the purpose and scope of the ontology, to represent both the customer and end-users, to facilitate communication between ontology development team and the customer	Decision-making, problem-solving, storytelling, creativity, application knowledge
Domain Expert	To provide general knowledge pertaining to the domain of the ontology, to supply ontology development team with definitions of concepts specific to the target domain or application, to provide definitions and explanation of concepts from existing standards, corpus, and other ontologies.	Domain knowledge, subject-matter expertise, awareness of relevant standards, corpus, and related ontologies for the target domain.
Ontology Analyst	To translate business needs into ontology requirements, to ensure proper documentations of requirements, to define the scope and prioritize development, to verify that requirements are satisfied by proper testing of the ontology	Ontology requirement engineering, critical thinking, negotiation skill, interpersonal skill

R1.2: The activities of Ontology requirements specification **SHOULD** follow the BPMN diagram given in Figure 1.

R1.2.1: The requirements specification **SHOULD** start from gathering use cases and data sets following the guidelines in R1.3: and R1.5:.

R1.2.2: From the use cases and data sets, the purpose and scope of the ontology **SHOULD** be identified following the guidelines in R1.6:.

R1.2.3: From the use cases and data sets, a set of user stories is collected as the intended use of the ontology following the guidelines in R1.7:.

- R1.2.4:** From the user stories, a set of competency questions is developed as the functional requirement for the ontology following the guidelines in R1.8:
- R1.2.5:** From the competency questions, a set of terms is extracted in a glossary following the guidelines in R1.9.:
- R1.2.6:** The outputs of the above activities are encoded in the Ontology Requirement Specification Document (ORSD) following the guidelines in R1.10.:
- R1.3:** The ontology development team **SHOULD** perform a series of interviews with the product owner and other users to gather Use cases and Data sets.
- R1.4:** The Ontology analyst **SHOULD** collect and document use cases in the following template given in **Error! Reference source not found.** by consulting the Product owner. The Ontology analyst **MAY** also take help from a Domain expert to fill up the template.
- R1.4.1:** More than one use case specification **MAY** be created for a project.

Figure 1: BPMN diagram for ontology requirement specification phase

Table 2: Use case specification template

<h3>3. Use Case Specification - <identifier/name></h3>	
Introduction: <i>(Short description of the use case)</i>	
Use case owner:	<i>(Short description of the use case)</i>
Involved partners:	<i>(Product owner / Customer / Client / Vendor / Supplier / knowledge scientist/engineer / material scientist)</i>
Purpose of ontology application	<i>(Data model / data structuring / Data sharing / Overview and visualization / Context bridging in digital communication / Software customization / Artificial Intelligence / Service extension / Business planning / communication / Decision System / Innovation Project Workflow / QA/QC / Guided AI / Data Parsing / Data Integration Interoperability / Others)</i>
Data sources used:	<i>(Mention what data describe; source of data, e.g., database, API, diagram, text; format of data, e.g., csv, tsv, xml, json, text)</i>
Ontologies considered:	<i>(Mention if any existing ontology is used)</i>
Main Challenges:	<i>(Main challenges that the clients are facing in the current scenario)</i>
Description: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Context of the use case: <i>(Describe the context in which the use case takes place, e.g., acquiring leads in a marketing campaign, material handling in an assembly line)</i> 2) What are the pre-conditions of your use case? <i>(Describe the states of the system and environment before the use case scenario starts)</i> 3) What are the post-conditions of your use case? <i>(Describe the states of the system and environment after the use case scenario ends)</i> 4) Who are the actors involved? <i>(List of all actors mentioned in the scenario steps)</i> 5) What are the steps of the main scenario? 	

(Please add here a picture that describes the aforementioned user story, in a compact way with discrete steps, e.g., workflow. An additional picture in the form of a use case UML diagram with connections to actors and software/hardware components would also be helpful.)

- 6) **Which data sources are used?** *(Please cross-reference with the steps of the main scenario)*
- 7) **What are the major (expected) contributions of this project to the use case?** *(Describe how the project's outcome will mitigate the challenges of this use case)*
- 8) **Name the most important 20 terms for the domain of your use case.** *(If available, please add any diagrams illustrating these terms (e.g., UML diagram, ER diagram))*

Implementation plan:

(Provide a rough time plan for your implementation. Particularly, list the milestones or scenario steps - by when what will be developed. Mention any additional resources that will be available during the project and associated constraints. Include any policy or protocol that the customer wants to follow.)

FAIR plan:

- 1) **Is there any existing plan for FAIRness?** *(Does the customer have an existing FAIRness strategy)*
- 2) **What are the future steps to improve FAIRness?** *(What does the demonstrator want to improve? If there are no/little improvements made and/or foreseen, motivate why. If there is an interest in progress here, what are the roadblocks?)*

Technology readiness level: *(Follow the guides¹² for assigning TRLs)*

- 1) of different scenario steps
- 2) of the application of ontology
- 3) of different tools involved

Key Performance Indicators (KPI): *(Provide the KPIs, corresponding metrics, and expected improvement by the end of the project)*

¹ Mitchell, J.A., Measuring the Maturity of a Technology: Guidance on Assigning a TRL, SAND2007-6733, Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, October 2007.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level

KPI	Metric	Current	Future

R1.5: The Ontology analyst SHOULD collect datasets, regulations, standards, data formats, API specifications, and database schemas from the customer (mediated by the Product owner).

R1.5.1: The Ontology analyst SHOULD document the purpose, type, and origin of the data along with any security concerns.

R1.5.2: The Ontology analyst SHOULD mention the related use case.

R1.5.3: The Ontology analyst SHOULD document how the data can be accessed.

R1.5.4: The Ontology analyst SHOULD document how long the data will be available when it will be updated and any other restrictions on its use.

R1.5.5: Ontology analysts SHOULD analyze the data for extracting potential features and the relationships among them in consultation with the domain expert and product owner.

1.5.5.1. For a set of APIs, the JSON data model MAY be documented. In this analysis, the API specification document and sample of API requests and responses MAY be considered as supporting evidence.

1.5.5.2. For relational data in database tables, the schema for tables, fields, relationships and viewed MAY be documented along with constraints using both primary and foreign keys.

1.5.5.3. For comma-separated, tab-separated files, and spreadsheets (common for logs, and records) the fields MAY be documented as well and more persistent storage of the record, possibly in some databases MAY be investigated for more information.

1.5.5.4. For unstructured data, e.g., free text, images, and audio, common metadata for the data files MAY be collected. Exploring the unstructured data requires further processing. These techniques are out of the purview of this guide.

R1.5.6: Every set of data should be documented by using the template in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 3: Data set/Data exchange specification template

DATA SET/Data Exchange Format n. # – <title of the data set> Owner(s): <organisation>						
1. DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data*					
	Type and Format of data*					
	Reused-Data					
	Data origin					
	Data size / Data exchange frequency					
	Data security and storage					
	Discoverability of data or API specification (metadata)					
	Use case #					
2. DATA STRUCTURE	Name of columns or fields or objects	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Name	Description		
	Name	Description				
	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies					
	Identifiability of data/transaction or primary and foreign key					
Naming conventions used						
Data model/schema/entity-relation diagram						
3. DATA ACCESS	Database/repository/folder path/URI					
	Sample queries					
	Methods or SW tools for data access					
	SW documentation and other information needed					
	Join conditions, filters, aggregation					
	Search keywords approach					

4. DATA AVAILABILITY	Timing of data availability (incl. indications on embargo)	
	Data update cycle	
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	
	Restrictions to data use/Access control	
	Expiration date	
5. DATA OWNERSHIP	Data owner	
	Data manager	

R1.6: The purpose and scope identification activity task **MUST** be carried out by domain experts, product owners, and ontology analysts.

R1.6.1: The purpose and scope **MUST** be identified by analyzing the use cases and the domain documentation provided in the data exchange identification.

R1.6.2: The purpose statements **SHOULD** provide a set of “completion criteria” for the ontology engineering project. The statements in the purpose **SHOULD** include the following aspects:

- a) Statements on the needs of the project, e.g., statement of need identifying the source of the request (person or project) and paraphrasing the stated motivations for the project.
- b) Statements on the objectives that the output of the project should satisfy, e.g., decision support system, integration of system, query answering system, improvement of reliability and quality, communication among departments, entities, and systems, knowledge acquisition, automation, classification, detection, and prediction. The statement of objectives should be “SMART”, i.e., specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound.
- c) Statements on the usage of ontology in data management tasks, e.g., annotation, configuration, filtering, indexing, integration, matching, mediation, personalization, query formulation, query rewriting, and search.

R1.6.3: The objectives included in the purpose **SHOULD** be quantified in terms of KPIs.

R1.6.4: The scope statements **SHOULD** define the context of the project in terms of:

- a) The topics which the ontology covers and which it should not, e.g., domain or application area, phases of the lifecycle, types of activities, types of resources, part of the system, list of protocols, genre, practice, paradigm, and types of documents.

- b) The viewpoint the ontology commits to, e.g., the perspective of the user, frame of reference, and mission and vision of the client's organization.
- c) The level of detail for the ontology development effort, e.g., existing ontology to be exploited, existing standards to follow, various format-related requirements (IRI format, encoding format etc.), level of expressivity, and intended end users.

R1.6.5: The scope statements **MAY** be updated at a later stage of the project by the assessment of the ontology analyst in agreement with the product owner.

R1.6.6: The scope analysis **MAY** bring out several non-functional requirements, especially from R1.6.4:c).

R1.7: A set of user stories **MUST** be extracted from the use cases and datasets by ontology analysts while being supported by domain experts, and the product owner.

R1.7.1: For each user story, a sample of data **MAY** be associated if required.

R1.7.2: Each user story **SHOULD** be identified with a numbering scheme.

R1.8: The Functional Ontology Requirement Proposal **MUST** be prepared by ontology analysts while being supported by domain experts, and the product owner.

Definitions

Competency Questions: Given a use case, the set of queries which place demands on an underlying ontology for a certain level of expressiveness such that the ontology must be able to represent these questions using its terminology and be able to characterize the answers to these questions using the axioms and definitions, is called competency questions.

Informal Competency Questions: The competency questions that are not yet expressed in the formal language of the ontology are called informal competency questions³.

Formal Competency Questions: The competency questions that are defined formally as an entailment or consistency problem with respect to the axioms in the ontology.

R1.8.1: Functional Ontology Requirements **SHOULD** be materialized as Competency Questions.

R1.8.2: Informal Competency questions **MAY** be derived from user stories extracted from use cases as mentioned in R1.7.:

R1.8.3: Informal Competency Questions **MUST** be written by the ontology analyst with the help of the domain expert.

³ By specifying the relationship between the informal competency questions and the motivating scenario, we give an informal justification for the new or extended ontology in terms of these questions. This also provides an initial evaluation of the new or extended ontology; the evaluation must determine whether the proposed extension is required or whether the competency questions can already be answered by existing ontologies.

- R1.8.4:** The competency questions SHOULD be defined in a stratified manner, with higher-level questions requiring the solution of lower-level questions⁴.
- R1.8.5:** For any competency question, the rationale MAY be specified for the question (which states how the answer to the question is used to answer more complex questions) and/or specify the decomposition of the question (simpler questions which we must answer to answer the given question).
- R1.8.6:** Every proposal for a new or extension of the existing purpose and scope and associated amendment to the use case SHOULD be covered by a set of additional competency questions.
- R1.8.7:** The template given in Table 4 MAY be used to write and manage informal competency questions.
- R1.8.8:** The set of competency questions MUST be checked for their validity and completion by the product owner and ontology analysts.
- 1.8.8.1. The set of completion criteria given below SHOULD be used for this validity and completion test.
- A set of competency questions is correct if each competency question is about some aspect of a user story that needs to be modelled by the ontology.
 - A set of competency questions is complete if no additional competency question is required to be added to the set, i.e., there are no user stories which has some aspect that is not covered by the competency questions.
 - A set of competency questions is internally consistent if no conflicts exist between them, i.e., for every competency question, the assumption of correctness of its answer should not imply the answer to any other competency question is incorrect.
 - A set of competency questions is verifiable if there is a finite process with a reasonable cost that tests whether the final ontology satisfies each requirement, i.e., there should not be any competency question which requires access to additional data (not associated with the user story the competency question is about), manual interventions, or execution of algorithms to derive the answer.
 - A set of competency questions is comprehensible if every competency question is understandable to the product owner and the ontology analyst.
 - A set of competency questions is unambiguous if every competency question has only one possible answer for every situation.

⁴ It is not a well-designed ontology if all competency questions have the form of simple lookup queries; there should be questions that use the solutions to such simple queries.

- A set of competency questions is concise if every competency question is relevant, i.e., no duplicated or irrelevant competency question exists in the set.
- 1.8.8.2. The ontology analyst MAY declare the completion of the requirement analysis and signal the start of the implementation phase only when the set of competency questions passes the validity and completion test.

Table 4: Functional requirement specification template

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Question	Answer	Status	Higher level Question	Rationale	Comments	Extracted from (provenance)	Priority
Code (domain+id)	Code or label the sprint	An interrogative sentence	Number, Token, sub-sentences, or a complete sentence	Proposed, Accepted, Rejected, Pending, Deprecated	Code	Text	Text	Source of the collected CQ	High, medium, or low

Identifier: The requirement identifier needs to be unique for each requirement. A suitable naming convention needs to be decided by the project members, e.g., use case # + index, domain + index, application + index.

Sprint: The sprint of the requirement iteration. Multiple iterations may be undertaken at the beginning of the project. Separate sprints needs to be undertaken for new amendment to the purpose and scope of the use case as well as an update of the ontology.

Competency Question: The competency question.

Answer: The answer to the competency question.

Status: The status of the requirement might be: 1) proposed, 2) accepted, 3) rejected, 4) ongoing or 5) deprecated.

Higher Level Question: The # of competency questions that depend on the answer to this competency question to be answered.

Rationale: How the answer to the question is used to answer the higher-level question, e.g., provides constraints (structural, functional, quantitative, qualitative, spatial, temporal, causal etc.), provides data (create new instance, asserts new relation, record measurement etc.), provides assumptions (create new situation, initiation of process, new activity etc.).

Comment: Free text for keeping notes regarding the competency question.

Provenance: The provenance of the provided requirement (use case, interview, mail, etc.).

Priority: The priority of the requirement can be: 1) high, 2) medium, or 3) low.

R1.9: A list of terms **MUST** be identified from the informal competency questions in a glossary.

R1.9.1: The glossary **MUST** be built by the Ontology Analyst.

R1.9.2: The keywords (e.g., subject, object, and main verb) for every informal competency question and its corresponding answer (e.g., tokens) **SHOULD** be enlisted in the terminology.

R1.9.3: The competency questions from which a term is extracted **MUST** be indicated for that term.

R1.9.4: Every term **SHOULD** be explained by associating the intended meaning of the term in the corresponding competency question.

R1.9.5: Every term **MAY** be associated with other homonyms, synonyms, hyponyms, and meronyms from a reputed source, e.g., Wordnet, dictionary etc.

- Synonyms could be found for most of the terms while only some terms have homonyms.
- If the term is a composite then there exists some meronyms.

R1.9.6: The template given in Table 5 **MAY** be used to enlist the terms in the glossary.

Table 5: Glossary template

#	Term	Definition	CQ (comma-separated)	Identifiers	Synonym	Homonym	Hyponym	Meronym

#: Index of the terms.

Term: Single word or a phrase

Definition: The definition of the word that corresponds to the meaning in which the term is used in the corresponding competency questions. If the same term is used with different meanings in some competency questions then they should be enlisted with different indexes.

CQ identifiers: The list of CQs from which the term is extracted (separated by a comma).

Synonym: The words or phrases that mean exactly or nearly the same as the term (separated by a comma).

Homonym: Other meanings of the term (separated by a comma).

Hyponym: The words or phrases with broader meaning (superordinate or supertype) of the term if available.

Meronym: The words or phrases which correspond to the part of the entity defined by the term if available.

R1.9.7: The terms **MAY** be sorted according to their frequency of occurrence in the competency questions.

R1.9.8: The competency questions **MAY** be prioritized based on the frequency of the terms calculated in R1.9.7:.

R1.10: Once the ontology development team has all the information about the requirements, obtained from the activities described in R1.6.; R1.7.; R1.8.; R1.9.; and the Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) **MUST** be created following the template given in Table 6.

R1.10.1: Only one ORSD **SHOULD** be produced for each sprint of the project.

R1.10.2: An ORSD **MUST** contain "Name of the project", "Prepared by" (name of the person who signs off the ORSD), "Purpose", "Scope", "Functional Requirement", and "Glossary of Terms".

1.10.2.1. The output of R1.6.2: and R1.6.3: **SHOULD** go to the field "Purpose".

1.10.2.2. The output of R1.6.4: **SHOULD** go to the field "Scope".

1.10.2.3. The output of R1.7: **SHOULD** go to the field "Intended Uses".

1.10.2.4. The Functional Requirement table produced by the guideline of R1.8: **SHOULD** either be embedded or hyperlinked in the field "Functional Requirements".

1.10.2.5. The Glossary table produced by the guideline of R1.9: **SHOULD** either be embedded or hyperlinked in the field "Glossary of Terms".

R1.10.3: An ORSD **MAY** contain "Non-Functional Requirements".

1.10.3.1. The output of R1.6.6: **SHOULD** go to the field "Non-Functional Requirements".

Table 6: Ontology requirement specification template

Ontology Requirements Specification Document	
1	Name of the project and sprint
2	Prepared by
3	Purpose
4	Scope
5	Intended Uses
	User story # 1
	...
	User story # 2
	...
6	Ontology Requirements
	1. Non-Functional Requirements
	2. Functional Requirements
	<i>Link to Functional Requirement Specification</i>
7	Glossary of Terms
	<i>Link to the glossary</i>

4. Analysis of requirement for new use case

In this section, the requirements collected from UC19 (Linköping University) is presented. In this use case, the Materials Design Ontology (MDO) is used for semantic and integrated access to the computational materials databases in the OPTIMADE consortium, dealing with the heterogeneity of the databases in terms of underlying data models and use of terminology. The developed ontology will be used in ontology-driven data access and data integration for application in the materials design domain. Figure 2 shows an overview of how such an application would work. The framework includes a generic approach that can generate a GraphQL server based on ontologies for data integration. In the early prototype we use Materials Project and the Open Quantum Materials Database as databases to integrate. In addition, we implement a GraphQL client to allow users to easily select queries instead of writing GraphQL queries by themselves.

Figure 2: Overview of UC19

The ORSD document for UC19 is presented in Table 7 and the competency questions representing the functional requirements are given in Table 8.

Table 7: ORSD document for UC19

Ontology Requirements Specification Document	
1	<p>Purpose (mandatory)</p> <p>A major goal of this use case is to facilitate data access and integration between the databases in the OPTIMADE consortium by using Material Design Ontology (MDO). In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to conduct semantic querying over the OPTIMADE databases. There is a need for a GraphQL and MDO-based interface to the OPTIMADE databases. By making queries using MDO terminology and across multiple databases, MDO can facilitate data interoperability within the OPTIMADE consortium. Furthermore, it is necessary to investigate the compatibility of MDO and top level ontologies, with EMMO as a first candidate, with respect to ontological commitment.</p>
2	<p>Scope (mandatory)</p> <p>Database integration, data interoperability, ontology alignment, materials</p>
3	<p>Implementation Language (optional)</p> <p>MDO, EMMO, PROV-O, CHEBI, QUDT</p>

4	Intended End-Users (optional)
	Material designers, data steward, database users
5	Intended Uses
	To make semantic queries among multiple databases in the OPTIMADE consortium. To investigate the compatibility of MDO and EMMO.
6	Ontology Requirements
	1. Non-Functional Requirements

Table 8: Competency questions for UC19

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC19-1	UC interview D3.5	What can a materials property relate to?	Structure.
UC19-2	UC interview D3.5	How many computational methods are associated with a materials calculation?	Exactly one.
UC19-3	UC interview D3.5	What does a structure correspond to?	A specific space group.
UC19-4	UC interview D3.5	What performs a calculation?	Software program. Code.
UC19-5	UC interview D3.5	What is a structure a part of?	Material.
UC19-6	UC interview D3.5	What is the process by which a calculation is achieved?	A specific computational method.
UC19-7	UC interview D3.5	What can be input into a calculation?	Structure. Property.
UC19-8	UC interview D3.5	What are the calculated properties and their values produced by a materials calculation?	
UC19-9	UC interview D3.5	What are the input and output structures of a materials calculation?	
UC19-10	UC interview D3.5	What is the chemical formula of a structure?	
UC19-11	UC interview D3.5	What is the space group type of a structure?	
UC19-12	UC interview D3.5	What is the lattice type of a structure?	
UC19-13	UC interview D3.5	What is the computational method used in a materials calculation?	

5.Data Collection from Use Case

As part of the second half of the task T3.3, efforts were made to collect data from the demonstrators. First, the demonstrators were surveyed as part of the final validation (D5.6) whether they are willing to submit data from their project. However, the responses were weak as only get 5 demonstrators responding affirmatively. Furthermore, these five demonstrators were not willing to make their data open due to the concern of privacy. Rather collecting raw data, the focus was therefore shifted to collecting information on the data. By the time of writing this report, only two demonstrators submitted information on their data, which is presented below.

5.1 UC9: Ontology-based Maintenance

Table 9: Description of data set 1 for UC9

DATA SET n. 1 – <Glossary of domain terms about (laser cutting) tooling machines > Owner(s): <Adige S.p.A.>		
1. DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data*	To establish a glossary of domain terms with the goal of facilitating documentation translation and standardisation tasks.
	Type and Format of data*	Textual, serialized as a pdf document
	Reused-Data	n./a.
	Data origin	Domain knowledge of laser cutting machines domain experts
	Data size*	~ 1Mb
	Data Security and Storage	
	Data value (Long Term)	
2. FAIR DATA	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)*	N./a.
2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	Resolvable URI (https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-domain-glossary)
	Naming conventions used*	n./a.

	Search keywords approach	
	Clear versioning approach	Git versioning
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Open
	How data will be made available	GitHub https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-domain-glossary
	Methods or SW tools for data access	
	SW documentation and other information needed	
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-domain-glossary
	Access restrictions	<i>n./a.</i>
	Data interoperability assessment	The glossary is mapped to an ontology, which is mapped to ontologies belonging to OntoCommons' ecosystem.
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	No standard vocabulary nor ontology mapping, but an appropriate domain ontology [mettere link] that is mapped with the glossary
	Data licensing for wide reuse	MIT licence
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl.	Data openly accessible through [mettere licenza] from now on (now it is a preliminary version which will be finalized at the end of the project).

licenses)	indications on embargo)	Part of the mapped ontology is also openly accessible (the rest is kept only for company-internal re-use, as it contains sensible information on products)
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Data will be usable for third parties, as specified above, except for part of the ontology.
	Restrictions to data re-use	MIT licence
	Quality assurance process	Analysis by domain experts
	Length of time of data re-usability	Unlimited, as specified in MIT licence
3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	
	Data Management Responsibilities	A company-external ontology-expert.

Table 10: Description of data set 2 for UC9

DATA SET n. 2 – <Spreadsheet about (laser cutting) tooling machines concepts> Owner(s): <Adige S.p.A.>		
1. DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data*	To establish a structured vocabulary of domain terms with the goal of building an ontology of the domain, to use as a knowledge base, and to enhance machine learning pipelines
	Type and Format of data*	Tabular, serialized as an Excel spreadsheet
	Reused-Data	n./a.
	Data origin	Domain knowledge of laser cutting machines domain experts
	Data size*	~120 kb
	Data Security and Storage	
	Data value	

	(Long Term)	
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)*	N./a.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	Resolvable URI (https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-spreadsheet-master)
	Naming conventions used*	n./a.
	Search keywords approach	
	Clear versioning approach	Git versioning
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Open
	How data will be made available	GitHub: https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-spreadsheet-master
	Methods or SW tools for data access	
	SW documentation and other information needed	
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	https://github.com/kataph/machine-tools-spreadsheet-master
	Access restrictions	<i>n./a.</i>
	Data interoperability	The glossary is mapped to an ontology, which is mapped to ontologies belonging to OntoCommons'

	assessment	ecosystem.
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	No standard vocabulary nor ontology mapping, but an appropriate domain ontology [mettere link] that is mapped with the glossary
	Data licensing for wide reuse	MIT licence
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	Data openly accessible through [mettere licenza] from now on (now it is a preliminary version which will be finalized at the end of the project). Part of the mapped ontology is also openly accessible (the rest is kept only for company-internal re-use, as it contains sensible information on products)
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Data will be usable for third parties, as specified above, except for part of the ontology.
	Restrictions to data re-use	MIT licence
	Quality assurance process	Analysis by domain experts
	Length of time of data re-usability	Unlimited, as specified in MIT licence
3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	
	Data Management Responsibilities	A company-external ontology-expert.

5.2 UC2: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing

Table 11: Description of data set 1 for UC2

DATA SET n. 1 – BOSCH Welding data Owner(s): BOSCH		
1. DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data*	The data is about the welding process at Bosch factory. The data is used for the purpose of welding quality monitoring and production improvement.
	Type and Format of data*	The data is in xlsx-files or json files.
	Reused-Data	
	Data origin	
	Data size*	6 GB (Approx.)
	Data Security and Storage	
	Data value (Long Term)	
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)*	<p>There are several data, which are in the following three groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Machine setting parameter, which contains columns of operation ID, machine status, error code, validation date etc. Time series sensor data collected during the welding operation, including current, voltage, etc. Meta data setting, including the welding spot ID, program ID, spot type, cap type etc.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	BOSCH internal ID
	Naming conventions used*	
	Search keywords approach	

	Clear versioning approach	
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	
	How data will be made available	The data is currently located a Bosch intern server, we will check the confidential policy at Bosch and then make it available from outside.
	Methods or SW tools for data access	
	SW documentation and other information needed	
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	
	Access restrictions	
	Data interoperability assessment	
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	
	Data licensing for wide reuse	
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl.	

(through clarifying licenses)	indications on embargo)	
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	
	Restrictions to data re-use	
	Quality assurance process	
	Length of time of data re-usability	
3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	
	Data Management Responsibilities	

6. Persistence of Requirement Data

The ontology requirement specification phase conducted under T3.3 have produced a set of ORSD for several demonstration use cases and domains. The requirement data in these ORSD also includes a set of competency questions. Separately a common glossary has been prepared. These requirement data may be used by future ontology development projects in the domains of materials and manufacturing. Future efforts may also update the domain requirements with additional competency questions. It is therefore important to make these requirements persistent for future use by making them easily findable, accessible, Integrable and reusable (FAIR). In the following sections we describe the FAIR strategy for these requirements.

6.1 Annotation of requirement data

The requirement data is presented in D3.4 in ORSD templates and tables. Although the structure of the template and the tables are described in D3.4, no standard vocabulary is available for the entities in these documents. Therefore, a new ontology is developed as described below for describing the entities in the ORSD, functional requirement template, and the glossary.

The ORSD ontology model displayed in Figure 3 is constructed to represent ORSD (documents). The ontology extends the OntoCommons Ecosystem Knowledge Graph (ockg), described in D4.8, by reusing the *ockg:ORSD* concept, which is a subclass of *Document* class from Information Artifact Ontology (iao). The ORSD ontology declares several subclasses of *iao:document part* to represent the sections of ORSD, e.g., Purpose, Scope, Implementation Languages, End Users, Intended Uses, Ontology Requirement, and Glossary. Two subclasses of Ontology Requirement are

FunctionalRequirementSpecification and *NonFunctionalRequirementSpecification*, which represents the sections for functional and non-functional requirement sections of ORSD respectively. The table containing the competency questions is represented by the class *CompetencyQuestionTable* and the table containing the terms is represented by the class *GlossaryTable*, both of which is a subclass of *iao:table*, as part of the *FunctionalRequirementSpecification*. To represent the data in the table, two new subclasses of *iao:document* part, i.e., *TableRow* and *TableCell*, are added. *TableCell* is part of some *TableRow*, which is in turn part of some *iao:Table*. Each *TableCell* has a column description, represented by *TableColumnName*, which is a type of *iao:datum* label. For *CompetencyQuestionTable*, the instances for *TableColumnName* are *Identifier*, *Sprint*, *Competency Question*, *Answer*, *Status*, etc. and for *GlossaryTable*, the instances for *TableColumnName* are *Terms*, *Synonym*, *Source Competency Questions*, *Meronym*, and *Homonym*. Each ORSD is identified by either the use case or domain, both of which are subclasses of *Topic*. While domains are referenced by FAIR subject taxonomy (SRAO), the UseCase(s) reference the use case identifier. Currently, there is no plan to annotate the use cases, which are documented in D5.2 and D5.5. However, these use cases may be stored in a FAIR repository, so that they can be referenced by their permanent and resolvable URI.

The ontology is named *Ontology for Ontology Requirement Specification (ORSO)* with IRI <<https://ontocommons.eu/ontology/orso>>. The FAIR metadata of this ontology along with the source files are hosted in Industryportal.

Figure 3: Ontology model for representing ORSD

6.1 FAIRness of requirement data

Along with the annotation of the ORSDs by standard vocabulary as described in the last section, the metadata of the annotated ORSDs need to be exposed in a FAIR manner to enable consumers discover the ORSDs. The publication of FAIR metadata is crucial for increasing the exposure, discoverability, and facilitating access. For this purpose, we adopted FAIR data point⁵ (FDP) specification to curate the metadata for the annotated ORSDs. There are two primary justifications for adopting FAIR data point: FDP is completely based on semantic metadata standards that combines the best features of Data Catalog (DCAT)⁶ and Dublin Core⁷, along with the Linked Data Platform (LDP)⁸ and REST philosophy to provide the highest possible technical interoperability and navigation among datasets while being a relatively simple implementation. 2) FDP is one of the three-point FAIRification framework which is recommend by GO-FAIR initiative as a practical “how to” guidance to stakeholders seeking to go FAIR. Although we adopt the metadata specification of FDP

⁵ <https://specs.fairdatapoint.org/>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

⁷ <https://dublincore.org/>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/>

<https://www.ontocommons.eu/>

to described the annotated ORSDs, our goal is not create an infrastructure by using the reference implementation for metadata registration service and the web clients for editing metadata of FDP. As of now, the metadata will be stored in a separate JSON-LD file with a permanent and resolvable URI. To avail such infrastructure, we are in touch with FAIRSharing.org to register the metadata. For the latest update on this front, please refer to the data management plan (D7.4).

In Table 12 the metadata of FDP for OntoCommons domain ontology requirements (common-req) is given. This data point is reserved for only OntoCommons domain ontology requirements. two different catalogues are created, one containing the ORSDs for demonstrator's use cases, and the other containing the ORSDs for domain requirements.

Table 13 and Table 14 describes the metadata for these two catalogues. Each ORSD is a resource and an example of the metadata for the ORSD in Table 15. No distribution is yet made for this data point as of now. However, the metadata file along with the annotated ORSDs may be found at <https://github.com/PICS-LGP/ontocommons-requirement.git>.

Table 12: metadata for the FDP

< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/fdp > a fdp-o:FairDataPoint	
dc:title	"Domain ontology requirements"
dct:conformsTo	< https://www.purl.org/fairtools/fdp/schema/0.1/fdpMetadata >
dct:description	"This FAIR data point deploys catalogues containing ontology requirement specification documents (ORSD) which describes requirements for OntoCommons demonstrators use cases and domains in materials and manufacturing."
dct:hasVersion	1.0
dct:license	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
dct:publisher	OntoCommons
fdp-o:metadataldentifier	< https://purl.ontocommons.eu/requirement/orsd >
fdp-o:metadatalssued	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
fdp-o:metadatalmodified	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
dct:isReferencedBy	D3.4-First Report on Domain Ontology requirements and specifications
fdp-o:metadatalcatalog	< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/85bc4c25-21da-4312-852f-a3670e2e4294 > < https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/domain/35631a15-b3cd-4fe4-8bb3-997401903e50 >

Table 13: Metadata for catalogues containing ORSD for use cases.

< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/85bc4c25-21da-4312-852f-a3670e2e4294 >	
a dcat:Catalog	
dc:title	"Domain ontology requirements"
dct:conformsTo	< https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#Catalog >
dct:description	"This catalogue contains ontology requirement specification documents (ORSO) which describes ontology requirements for OntoCommons demonstrator use cases."
dct:hasVersion	1.0
dct:license	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
dct:publisher	OntoCommons
fdp-o:metadataIdentifier	< https://purl.ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/85bc4c25-21da-4312-852f-a3670e2e4294 >
fdp-o:metadataIssued	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
fdp-o:metadataModified	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
dct:hasPart	< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/ORSO/33d13ecb-414f-4a28-a2ef-dab7061a26f4 >

Table 14: Metadata for catalogues containing ORSD for domain requirements

< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/domain/35631a15-b3cd-4fe4-8bb3-997401903e50 >	
a dcat:Catalog	
dc:title	"Domain ontology requirements"
dct:conformsTo	< https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#Catalog >
dct:description	"This catalogue contains ontology requirement specification documents (ORSO) which describes ontology requirements for the domains in materials and manufacturing."
dct:hasVersion	1.0
dct:license	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
dct:publisher	OntoCommons
fdp-o:metadataIdentifier	< https://purl.ontocommons.eu/requirement/domain/35631a15-b3cd-4fe4-8bb3-997401903e50 >

fdp-o:metadataIssued	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
fdp-o:metadataModified	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
dct:keyword	ORSD, Requirement, Ontology
dct:hasPart	< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/ORSD/bcad5d6b-a76d-4229-9bde-ea651074df2a >

Table 15: Example metadata of ORSD resource for UC11 Siemens

< https://ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/ORSD/33d13ecb-414f-4a28-a2ef-dab7061a26f4 > a dcat:Catalog	
dc:title	"Ontology requirements for OntoCommons use case 11 Siemens"
dct:conformsTo	< https://www.ontocommons.eu/ontology/orso >
dct:description	"This resource represents ontology requirement specification documents (ORSD) for use case 11: Siemens"
dct:hasVersion	1.0
dct:license	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
dct:publisher	OntoCommons
fdp-o:metadataIdentifier	< https://purl.ontocommons.eu/requirement/app/ORSD/33d13ecb-414f-4a28-a2ef-dab7061a26f4 >
fdp-o:metadataIssued	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
fdp-o:metadataModified	2023-09-15T00:00:00.000Z
dct:issued	2022-02-20T00:00:00.000Z
dct:modified	2022-02-20T00:00:00.000Z
dcat:contactPoint	Maja Milicic Brandt (maja.milicicbrandt@siemens.com)

7. Conclusions

Report D3.5 enhances the original report D3.4 on domain ontology requirements and specifications. First, a standardised ontology requirement methodology based on the observations and feedback gathered during T3.3. Second, result of the requirement analysis for new demonstrator use case is included. Third, the effort on collecting data from demonstrators is reported. And finally, a strategy for storing and sustaining the requirement specification data is presented. The motivation behind persisting the collected requirements in FAIR -enabled repository is to provide the community to use them in the future for several domain specific ontology development. In this way they will act as a benchmark for verifying the existing and future domain ontologies. When coupled with the OntoCommons Ecosystem stack of ontology, methodology and tools, these requirements will help in assuring that the domain ontologies cover the core requirements of the domains. The relevance of these requirements for that purpose is ensured as they were collected from the feedbacks from not only the OntoCommons demonstrators but also external experts and stakeholders from various domains, as described in D3.4 and D3.5.

The requirements are a live set of documents which are not closed to further update. In fact, the FAIR profiles associated with them provides a way to maintain the versions for future updates. This report also provides a standard guideline to capture requirements for harmonising such post-project activities. Needless to say, the applicability of these guidelines and the set of requirements produced by the effort of T3.3 of OntoCommons project goes beyond the scope of domains of manufacturing and materials and could be replicated for ontology requirement engineering in many other domains.